

Relationship between ISO 9001:2008 Certification and Service Quality of Kenya Plant Health Inspectorate Service in Nairobi Kenya

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to establish a relationship between ISO 9001:2008 certification and service quality of Kenya Plant Health Inspectorate Services (KEPHIS). The study was informed by Deming's theory. The study adopted correlational research design. The target population was 130 respondents from KEPHIS. A sample size of 97 respondents was chosen for the study. The data collection instrument that was used to collect was questionnaires and interview schedule. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentages and means and inferential statistics which included the Pearson correlation and regression analysis. The findings revealed that customer focus has a positive and significant effect on service quality. However, system approach management does not have a significant effect on service quality. The study concludes that customer focus is critical towards enhancing the quality of service of the organization. From the findings of the study, the study recommends organization under the guidance of the management to set up systems that would enhance their level of interaction with the customers.

Keywords: System Approach, Customer Focus, ISO, KEPHIS, Service Quality

Introduction

Improving the quality of service is one factor in business survival, but cost and speed of service are also vital. It has been suggested that a firm cannot achieve success in today's business environment without delivering superior service quality (Lai, 2007). Globally, most organizations have various ways of enhancing their service quality provision although the ways vary from one organization to another depending on the actual functions of each organization. This is done in a bid to improve the performance of the organizations. Meisinger and Wagner (2013), state that in the majority of organization worldwide, ISO certification is the most important management tool for performance and for organizations to perform well, resources must be well utilized and customers well served. To achieve such ends, all of an organization's human and materials resources must be well utilized in the right way and the right time to create high service quality's at minimal cost. ISO 9001 certification has emerged as the most important organizational phenomenon in most organizations including the health sector that enables managers to harness the energies of all employees to determine their strength and maximize productivity and customer satisfaction. It is now generally accepted that ISO 9001:2008 certification has become the most prevalent global quality initiative (Tsiotras & Gotzamani, 2013).

The ISO 9000 provide guidance and tools for all organizations that want to ensure that their products and services consistently meet customers' requirements and that quality is consistently improved. The ISO 9000 family addresses various aspects of quality management and contains some of ISO's best-known standards (Vallabhanen, 2015). ISO 9000:2008 is a well-recognized family of standards whose theoretical background is the Total Quality Management, a managerial approach which aims to improve service quality and organization performance (Wanambisi, 2010). Among more than 18,000 standards published by ISO (International Organization for Standardization), ISO 9001 is particularly important because it is the most widespread (Downs, 2012).

In Africa, despite the growing interest and importance of ISO 9001 certification in many organizations, the implementation of such innovations in African organizations and especially some sectors has remained low, the

adoption rates among clients and its usage has not brought significant outputs in the way organizations perform and clients become happy with the services offered (Zeithaml, Valerie, and Bitner, 2010). For instance, this has been seen in Uganda, Zimbabwe, and Cameroon that some of the organizations have adopted the ISO 9001 certification aspects however its implementation has not been effective. One of the benefits the organizations derive from ISO 9001 certification in operations especially with respect to service quality is improved efficiency and effectiveness of their operations so that more controls, evaluation, planning, and implementation can be processed faster and most conveniently, which will undoubtedly impact significantly on the overall quality of service provision of the organization (Edgar, 2011)

Stakeholders in Kenya are becoming increasingly more sophisticated, better informed and more demanding on the ISO 9001 certification implementation in their organizations. A lot of emphasis has been put on ISO 9001 certification, with all ministries and public institutions required to be ISO certified by 2012 and government favoring ISO certified suppliers during procurement processes (Macharia, 2010). According to ISO Survey-2008, in East and Central Africa, Kenya was found to be having the highest number of ISO 9001 certifications with a total of 257, followed by Uganda with 44 and Tanzania 12 (Macharia, 2010). Out of the 257 ISO 9001 certified, 20 were manufacturing companies of which 15 were in Nairobi. Despite the number research on ISO 9000 and service quality offered in developed countries, little information exists on ISO 9000 experiences in the developing countries particularly Kenya.

Customer needs and expectations are changing when it comes to government services and their quality requirements. However, service quality practices in public sector organizations are slow and are further exacerbated by the poor quality management system (Teicher, 2002). Public service efficiency in the delivery of results/services has been a challenge in the world and particularly in the third world countries. In most African countries and particularly in Kenya, the public service for a long time has been characterized by the corruption, low productivity inefficiency, lack of transparency and accountability (Reson and Lydia, 2015). There has been major complains by Kenyan over poor service delivery by government institution such as KEPHIS.

ISO 9001:2008 quality management system standards are meant to enable organizations to set up effective and efficient management systems for them to meet the needs of interested parties including business goals, society, employees, customer and regulatory authorities and assure sustained success (Alima, 2014). In Kenya, one of the approaches that widely supported to deliver and is promoted by the World Bank is the ISO 9001 certification. However, despite most organizations in both the public and the private sector in Kenya embracing ISO certification as a way of contributing to customer satisfaction and staff motivation as well as having an international standard on which they are operating, most government institutions are experiencing challenges in offering service qualities.

Many researchers tried to find the impact of ISO 9001 certification on all types of firms and companies around the world, however most of this study have provided inconclusive results for example, a study by Magd (2011) and Chris (2014) showed a positive effect of ISO 9000 while others such as Terziovski (2014) and Kumar and Balakrishnan (2011) found a negative impact effect from the ISO 9001 certification. Moreover, there have been limited studies addressing how ISO 9001:2008 influence service quality among government institutions in Kenya such as KEPHIS. If such evaluation studies are not conducted quality performance will decline, and customers will not be satisfied with service delivery. Therefore this study sought to find out the relationship between ISO 9001:2008 certification and service quality of Kenya health services head office Nairobi. Thus, the study hypothesized that:

- i. *There is a relationship between customer focus and service quality at KEPHIS*
- ii. *There is a relationship between system approach management and service quality at KEPHIS*

Theoretical Framework

This study adopted Deming's theory of on a quest for quality which states that; "Quality is everyone's responsibility." Deming (1990-1993) is considered to be the father of Modern Quality. He preached that to achieve the highest level of performance requires more than a good philosophy-the organization must change its behavior and adopt new ways of doing business. Deming's theory emphasizes on continuous improvement which is one of the principles of ISO 9001:2008. It helps organizations to remain competitive and improve the quality of products. Deming came up with 14 points, and the 5th point is to improve constantly the system of production and service.

Deming (1986) said, "Quality must be built at the design stage" This theory is therefore relevant to the study since it emphasizes the need for continuous improvement in order to produce service quality. Building on Total Quality Management (TQM) model as espoused by Deming, with a working model in place, a company should be able to support the structure with a series of drivers that translate the model into working vehicles. These drivers add guidance to the vehicles that carry the program into a series of actions creating the TQM climate focused on Customer Satisfaction and quality. The study utilized these theories to ascertain the relationship between implementing ISO 9001 -2008 in public institutions at KEPHIS.

Empirical Review

A study was carried out in Pakistan by Cox (2013) in the impact of customer focus on service quality: A case of Banking Sector. The objective of the study was to investigate the effect of quality on satisfaction by focusing on the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction and how quality can be improved in the service firms.

The findings revealed that quality of service does affect the customer satisfaction up to some certain level as both concepts are distinct and the relationship found between them is casual. Also, the quality of service has a significant contribution towards customer satisfaction because it is affected by various factors such as human interaction, physical environment, value, price, performance, etc. To improve performance system companies should focus more on introducing employee-oriented policies by establishing a service culture followed by a strong strategy in place and by removing gaps between management employees and its customers. It is found that through proper planning and constant monitoring firms can develop effective strategies to improve quality levels and to retain their existing & future customers.

The study concluded that the most important issue to win customer's trust is to focus on developing customer complaint resolution system. As the main focus is on satisfying the customer who demands to put an extra effort to understand their concerns. Sometimes a little nod or a smile can make a customer feel valued. There are small things like gestures, a way of dealing even dressing can be used as an inspirational technique. Also, it's important to deal the customer in a way he/she understands. If we consider banks particularly, people who visit the bank belong to different age groups so bank should deal them in their way according to their comfort level.

A study carried was carried out by Crosby (2015) in Syria on effects of customer focus on customer satisfaction: an empirical investigation in mobile telecommunication services. The objective of the study was to analyze the effects of service quality dimensions on Customer Satisfaction in Syrian mobile phones companies and strives to develop a valid and reliable instrument to measure customer perceived service quality incorporating both service delivery as well as technical quality aspects. The findings of this study showed the significant direct impact of service quality on customer satisfaction, and this effect had appeared through three dimensions (network quality, responsiveness, reliability) and there are no direct effects of other dimensions on

customer satisfaction. Syrian companies must know how to provide superior network quality which is considered as critical by the respondents in judging the quality of mobile communication services and satisfaction in the Syrian context.

In conclusion, the research resulted in the development of a reliable and valid instrument for assessing customer perceived service quality for cellular mobile services. The resulting instrument is devised after a review of the literature and exploratory investigations followed by a series of acceptable validation procedures. On the basis of the findings revealed during the exploratory investigations, complaint handling, convenience and customer perceived network quality dimensions were added in the original SERVQUAL scale. Factor analysis indicates that network quality operates as a stand-alone dimension while responsiveness and compliant handling were merged as one to maintain high internal consistency, this also represents that respondents perceived both the dimensions as one. Further, the study highlighted the relative importance of service quality attributes; an attempt was made to identify the contribution of each service quality dimensions in predicting overall customer satisfaction.

A study by Furrer (2010) on the relationship between ISO 9001:2008 and implementing quality management systems on surgical patient care: experience whose objectives were; to establish the determinants of quality management system uptake in a hospital setting and the relationship between ISO 9001:2008 and implementing QMS on patient care. The study methodology was a cross-sectional research which utilized quantitative and qualitative research methods. A sample of 96 nurses chosen by simple random and purposeful sampling and working in a surgical unit was involved. Data was collected using 5 point Likert scale questionnaires, key informants guide, and documentary reviews. The study revealed that the aim for ISO certification was to standardize and to improve the quality of care. Efficiency in the provision of care had improved especially retrieval of records, clear work instruction, and improved documentation. The documentary review indicated a consistent customer satisfaction of 75%, an increase in bed occupancy of 10% but no change in length of stay. The study Conclusion and recommendations were Quality Management system was implemented in a public hospital with the aim of improving service delivery. Understanding requirements of QMS are critical in its implementation, though one needs to overcome increased documentation which is seen as a major challenge. Implementation of QMS improved aspects of care, but others had not improved significantly. Use of performance indicators may provide a reliable measure of the relationship between ISO 9001:2008 and QMS on quality of care.

Golafshani (2011) carried out a study on assessment of the effect ISO 9001:2008 certification on service quality. The study sought to address the effect of ISO 9001:2008 certification in improving service quality and it was guided by the following objectives; to assess the effects of ISO 9001 certification on organizational productivity, to establish the effects of ISO 9001 certification on quality of service, to examine the effects of ISO 9001 certification on cost of service and to determine the effects of ISO 9001 certification on reputation of an organization. The study was necessitated by the lack of ample literature linking ISO 9001 certification to service quality. A case study research design was adopted in the study. The study focused on 20 top managers, 48 middle-level managers, and 235 operational managers. The study findings indicated that ISO 9001 certification has led to an increase in the number of customers in the Hospital. Also, that ISO 9001 certification has led to the provision of work instructions and favorable working environment that ensures efficiency in task performance. There's also an indication that ISO 9001 certification has improved performance in organizations through prevention of defects and has also helped to improve the reputation of the organization through providing a unique image in the market. However, the study also points out that ISO certification remains an expensive tool to apply in the organizational processes due to the high costs associated with maintaining the standards. This is especially true since reworking of processes for example contract procedures and order placements is a common occurrence in order to meet the customer requirements. In order to improve

performance through ISO 9001 certification, the study recommends that the top management of the hospital should be committed and active in implementing the requirements stipulated in the ISO 9001:2008 certification. Regular training as well as adhering to teamwork approach should also be applied. The study concluded that top management should also adopt ISO 9001:2008 as a marketing tool since it has been observed that the certification helps improve the company's image.

Material and methods

The study adopted a correlational research design. The study targets a total of 130 employees from KEPHIS which included 1 Managing director, 3 General Managers, 14 Section heads and 112 other employees. A sample size of 97 respondents was chosen for the study. The study employed purposive sampling to select managing director and general managers while simple random sampling was used to select section heads and other employees based at Headquarters. Simple random sampling was used to avoid biases and every individual to have an equal chance to participate in the study. The study used primary data which was collected through the drop and pick questionnaires. This study utilized secondary data by use of content analysis which was obtained from the KEPHIS annual reports, Quality management reports, magazines and articles. Cronbach's coefficient alpha method was used to determine the internal consistency of the items. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The inferential statistics involved the use of multiple regression analysis techniques.

Findings

Sample characteristics

This section shows the demographic characteristics of the respondents including gender, the age of the respondent, the highest level of educational qualification and the length of continuous service with the organization.

Table 1: sample characteristics

Characteristic		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	49	52.7
	Female	44	47.3
	Total	93	100
What is your age bracket	21-30 yrs	9	9.7
	31-40 yrs	18	19.4
	41-50 yrs	35	37.6
	51-60 yrs	31	33.3
	Total	93	100
What is your highest level of educational qualification?	Postgraduate	19	20.4
	Undergraduate	24	25.8
	Tertiary college	31	33.3
	Secondary	19	20.4
	Total	93	100
Length of continuous service with the organization?	0-5 yrs	4	4.3
	6-10 yrs	39	41.9
	11-15 yrs	41	44.1
	16-20 yrs	9	9.7
	Total	93	100

Customer Focus

This section of the analysis focused on customer knowledge. The findings are as presented in Table 2. The respondents were asked to provide their responses regarding customer focus. The results from the study revealed that The mean value was 3.86 and standard deviation 0.92 implying that there is a suggestion box for

customers to give feedback on the service of the organization. Regarding the views of the respondents on whether the institutions have created a website for customer services, the mean value of 3.73 and standard deviation of 0.81 implied that the institutions had created a website for customer services. In determining whether the institutions have customer care desk within adequate customer care employees, 50.5% (47) agreed, The mean response of 3.73 and standard deviation of 0.85 implies that the institutions have customer care desk To assess whether the institutions have adequate customer care employees, the mean value of 3.91 and standard deviation of 0.92 means that the institutions have adequate customer care employees In general, the results of customer focus summed up to a mean of 3.81 and standard deviation of 0.87 meaning that the respondents were agreeable on most of the items on customer focus. On the other hand, the standard deviation of less than 1 indicates that there is less variation in the responses.

Table 2: Customer Focus

Statement	Mean	Standard Dev.
There is suggestion box for customer to give feedback on our service KEPHIS	3.86	0.92
The institutions have created a website for customer services	3.73	0.81
The institutions have customer care desk within adequate customer care employees	3.73	0.85
The institutions have created a website for customer services	3.91	0.92
Customer Focus	3.81	0.87

System Approach management

This section of the analysis highlights the results on system approach management. The findings are presented in Table 3. Regarding whether there is efficiency in KEPHIS operations hence reduction in cost that would have been incurred and factored in customers' accounts, The mean response of 3.63 and standard deviation of 0.98 implied that majority of the respondents were in agreement that there is efficiency in KEPHIS operations hence reduction in cost that would have been incurred and factored in customers' accounts. The study also sought to establish whether due to ISO certification standards, KEPHIS has increased access to donor funding which in turn helps in reducing cost and from the findings, the mean response of 3.62 and standard deviation of 0.91 meant that majority of the respondents were in agreement that due to ISO certification standards KEPHIS has increased access to donor funding which in turn helps in reducing cost.

Regarding whether ISO certification has helped in preventing defects in service quality hence reduced cost that would have been incurred in attending to them after they occurred, 50.5% (47) agreed, the mean response of 3.34 and standard deviation of 0.93 meant that majority of the respondents agreed that ISO certification has helped in preventing defects in service quality hence reduced cost that would have been incurred in attending to them after they occurred. Finally, the study also sought to determine whether there is a systematic way of managing the KEPHIS, which affects consistency in their operations and reduction of rework job hence reduction in cost. The findings revealed that the mean response of 3.54 and standard deviation of 0.70 implied that majority of the respondents agreed that there is a systematic way of managing the KEPHIS, which affects consistency in their operations and reduction of rework job hence reduction in cost.

Table 3: System Approach Management

Statement	Mean	Standard Dev.
There is efficiency in KEPHIS operations hence reduction in cost that would have been incurred and factored in customers' accounts	3.63	0.98
Due to ISO certification standards, KEPHIS has increased access to donor funding which in turn helps in reducing cost	3.62	0.91
ISO certification has helped in preventing defects in service quality hence reduced the cost that would have been incurred in attending to them after they occurred.	3.34	0.93
There is a systematic way of managing the KEPHIS, which affects consistency in their operations and reduction of rework job hence reduction in cost	3.54	0.70
System Approach Management	3.53	0.88

Service Quality

This section illustrates the results on service quality. The findings were summarized and presented in Table 4. From the results on whether when he promised to do something we do it, The mean response of 3.41 and standard deviation of 1.15 indicated an overall agreement with the statement but with varied response.

The study also sought to determine whether they show sincere interest in solving customers problems for them and the mean response of 3.54 and standard deviation of 1.18 implied overall agreement that they show sincere interest in solving customers' problems for them. Regarding whether they are dependable, a mean response of 3.51 and standard deviation of 1.15 indicating that there was an overall agreement that they were dependable. Furthermore, the study sought to determine whether they provide services at the time they promise a mean response of 3.71 and standard deviation of 1.11 means that there is an overall agreement that the organizations provide services at the time they promise. Regarding whether the organizations keep statements accurately, the mean response of 3.75 and standard deviation of 1.00 implied a general agreement that the organizations keep statements accurately.

The study also sought to determine whether the institution's the institution's related service information can easily be obtained, and a mean response of 3.82 and standard deviation of 1.00 implied a general agreement that the institution's related service information can easily be obtained. Regarding on whether the institutions' employees promptly serve customers, a mean response of 3.83 and standard deviation of 0.73 indicated an overall agreement with the statement that the institutions' employees promptly serve customers hence improving on service quality and approval from the customers.

The study also sought to determine whether the institutions' employees are always willing serve to customers a mean response of 3.60 and standard deviation of 1.05 showed that there was overall agreement that the institutions employees are always willing to serve to customers which clearly showed that the employees were highly motivated and had passion for serving the customers and this is as a result of internal institutional strategies that enhance the morale of the employees.

Finally, the study sought to establish whether employees promptly respond to customers' requests even when they are busy, and the findings showed that the mean response of 3.70 and standard deviation of 1.12 showed that the employees promptly respond to customers' requests even when they are busy although the responses were varied as shown by the high standard deviation. Generally, results on service quality summed up to a mean of 3.65 and standard deviation of 1.054. From the foregoing, it can be deduced that the institutions have realized high service quality. There is also generally less variation among the responses as evidenced by the standard deviation.

Table 4: Service Quality

Statement	Mean	Standard Dev.
When promises to do something we do it	3.41	1.15
We show sincere interest in solving customers problems for them	3.54	1.18
We are dependable	3.51	1.15
We provide services at the time we promise	3.71	1.11
We keep statement accurately	3.75	1.00
The institution's related service information can easily be obtained	3.82	1.00
The institution's employees promptly serve customers	3.83	0.73
The institution's employees are always willing to serve to customers	3.60	1.05
Employees can promptly respond to customers' requests even when they are busy	3.70	1.12
Service Quality	3.65	1.054

Test of hypothesis

The findings on correlation were summarized and presented in Table 5. There was a strong relationship between customer focus and service quality ($r = 0.485$, p -value < 0.01). However, the study revealed no relationship between system approach management and service quality. The results in Table 5 showed that all the two predictors (customer focus, and system approach management) explained 82.7% variation in service quality (R squared = 0.827). The study findings in Table 5 indicated that the above-discussed coefficient of determination was significant as evidence of F ratio of $F = 105.265$ ($p = 0.000$). Thus, the model was fit to predict service quality using customer focus and system approach management.

The study findings showed that customer focus had a standardized coefficient of the estimate which was significant and positive, $\beta_1 = 0.163$ (p -value = 0.042 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$) implying that customer focus has a significant effect on service quality. Furthermore, the effect of customer focus was stated by the t -test value = 2.06 which implies that the effect of the parameter was more than the standard error associated with the parameter. The study findings revealed that customer focus has a positive and significant effect on service quality. These findings are consistent with the findings of a study carried out by Cox (2013) on the impact of customer focus on service quality and the findings revealed that quality of service does affect the customer satisfaction up to some certain level as both concepts are distinct, and the relationship found between them is casual, and it was concluded that the most important issue to gain customer's trust is to focus on developing a customer complaint resolution system because the main aim is to meet the customer needs. Consequently, in order to enhance the performance system, companies or institutions should focus more on introducing employee focused strategies by instituting a service culture followed by a strong strategy in place and by removing gaps between management employees and the customers of the company.

The findings showed that system approach management had a coefficient of the estimate which was not significant based on $\beta_2 = 0.152$ (p-value = 0.174 which is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$) thus we conclude that system approach management does not have a significant effect on service quality. The study findings also revealed that system approach management does not have a significant effect on service quality. In this study, Furrer (2010) concluded and recommended that Quality Management system was implemented in a public hospital with the aim of improving service delivery. Although this was the case, the implementation of QMS improved aspects of care, but others had not improved significantly. On the other hand, Golafshani, (2011) found out that ISO 9001 certification has led to an increase in the number of customers in the Hospital, led to the provision of work instructions and conducive working environment that ensures efficiency in task performance. However, the study also points out that ISO certification remains an expensive tool to apply in the organizational processes due to the high costs associated with maintaining the standards. In order to improve performance through ISO 9001 certification, the study recommends that the top management of the hospital should be committed and active in implementing the requirements stipulated in the ISO 9001:2008 certification. Regular training as well as adhering to teamwork approach should also be applied.

Table 5 : Coefficient of estimates

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			correlation zero-order	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.		Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	-0.534	0.23		-2.319	0.023			
Customer Focus	0.17	0.083	0.163	2.06	0.042	0.485	0.573	1.746
System Approach Management	0.152	0.111	0.117	1.371	0.174	0.147	0.41	2.441
R Square	0.827							
Adjusted R Square	0.819							
F Change	105.265							
Sig. F Change	0.000							

a Dependent Variable: Service Quality

Conclusion

Clearly, customer focus is critical towards enhancing the quality of service of the organization. Key among them is the provision of a favorable environment that would nurture and foster a healthy environment for the organization, its employees, and the customers. More importantly, having the ability to listen to the customers' feedback is critical towards change management in the organization both in quality of service and quality of relationships. The essence of having a customer suggestion box does not just about please the customer, but also it should be used as a means of observing the organization and its quality of service from the eyes or perspective of the customer and using that view to improve and provide better service. This can also be enhanced by providing a user-friendly website through which the customers can access to vital information as well as a customer care desk that can be used to address quickly and efficiently the concerns of the customers.

Ideally, system approach management should be essential among other factors if the organization or institution has a vision of achieving high performance through the improvement of service quality. The fact that the findings of this study have found system approach management to be not significant in influencing service quality implies that the organization or institution is not committed to setting aside adequate financial and non-financial resources that would propel the organization towards ISO certification. Furthermore, the employees have not been made aware of the benefits of ISO certification to the extent that even if the organization is ISO

certified, there would be little change in how processes are carried out. ISO certification has been found to be very important in enhancing the efficiency of operations, reduce operational costs, access funding and in preventing defects in service quality.

Recommendations

From the findings of the study, it is critical for the organization under the guidance of the management to set up systems that would enhance their level of interaction with the customers by providing an enabling environment through which the customer can express themselves and provide feedback about the services they receive. The feedback from the customers should also activate the development of meaningful strategies that would improve service quality. Although system approach management was not found to have a significant effect, it is critical towards improving the performance of the organization. Thus, to reap the benefits of ISO certification, the organization should be encouraged to utilize the effective internal mechanisms that would link service quality and the aims of the ISO certification and this can be achieved through continual training of the employees and set aside enough resources to implement processes that are geared towards realizing the objectives of the ISO certification. The role of system approach management was found to be not significant in determining service quality. There is need to carry out further research specifically focused on establishing the relationship between ISO certification and firm performance being moderated by external and internal organizational factors. This would essentially aid in establishing the factors that would impede the full implementation of ISO certification and how they can be mitigated so as to reap the benefits of ISO certification.

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